

RESEARCH ON THE SUPPLY OF HUMAN RESOURCES WITH SPECIAL NEEDS AND IMPACT ON THE LABOUR MARKET

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Abstract

Purpose – *The study explores the integration of people with special needs on the workforce.*

Methodology/approach – *The bibliographical study consults peer reviewed articles, specialty books, national and international databases, statistical databases, private and public institutions data, legislations and regulations, and so on.*

Findings – *People with special needs have a lower employment rate. Two prominent reasons are lack in accessibility – as disability is a relationship of individual and environment; and superficial perceptions of people with disabilities.*

Research limitations/implications – *Limitations arise from the everchanging situation, with especially hard to measure attitudes and hard to change norms. Even more, there are no universal and comparable ways to measure progress – should it be percentage of employed people, should it be proportion of people with special needs in positions of power?*

Practical implications – *The paper underlines the importance of first hand interactions with people with special needs, their visibility in regular environments.*

Originality/value – *It is valuable to analyse disability and workforce integration in a single model, giving a better insight into a more complete story and its interactions.*

Key words: *People with special needs, Workforce integration, Human resources*

Introduction

This study proposes the research of the management of integration of the human resource with special needs at an organizational level. Based on these considerations, the paper introduces the analysis of the necessary resources that the person with special needs must obtain from school and society to integrate into the labour market. It is essential to achieve the objectives, as well as to implement the most correct decisions for structuring a model.

The relevance and need of the research lie in the fact that over time, both the person with special needs and the labour market had been approached in the literature from different perspectives, yet rarely in relation to their interdependence. Many countries have committed themselves to implementing policies, laws and administrative measures that ensure the rights recognized in international conventions, laws, regulations, customs and human rights, practices that constitute discrimination (World Health Organization (WHO), 2011). Furthermore, in many European countries, the need to take a step forward in integration and in creating an inclusive labour market in which everyone can participate regardless of any form of disability or vulnerability is emphasized (European Disability Strategy 2010-2020, 2010).

Methodology

The proposed research model starts from highlighting the legislation that is meant to influence and determine the impact on people with disabilities.

The research directions are: bibliographical study on human resources with special needs and their integration into organizations in Romania; and research of the offer of human resources with special needs.

The stages of the bibliographic study are: bibliographic analysis of the legislation associated with human resources with special needs, the organizational characteristics involved in the integration of the human resource with special needs, the characteristics of the human resource with special needs, the characteristics of the manager in relation to the human resource with special needs.

The research continues through the identification and description of the most representative variables that characterize the dimensions of human resources with special needs as well as of the variables that characterize the organizations involved in hiring human resources with special needs.

Findings

The year 1981 marks a pivotal time and the beginning of a change in the paradigm of disability, as The United Nations declared it The International Year of Disabled Persons. Its focus was on participation and equality, meaning the right of people with special needs (PWSN) to fully be a part of the life and development of their societies (United Nations, n.d.). Disability got defined as the relationship between person and environment, thus it is not an attribute of an individual but created by the social environment, and requires social changes (Mitra, 2006). The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) is a framework developed by the WHO, and endorsed by 191 countries as of May 2001 (resolution WHA 54.21), making it the international standard to describe and measure health and disability. ICF is distinctive as it offers nuanced descriptions based on an interconnected model of impairments, activity limitations and participation restrictions.

Globalization influenced the matter by putting into effort more people to solve the issue. In this way developments could diffuse better and faster for the improvement of the lives of people with disabilities, them being a category with not enough research on national levels.

The European Commission estimated the disability percentage of the European population at 20 percent (European Commission, 2020), and WHO at 15 percent globally (WHO, 2011). While the proportion of PWSN on and in the labour force is unclear, the employment rate of PWSN is much lower as accounted by multiple sources: 52.8% for men with disability and 19.6% for women with disability, compared with 64.9% for non-disabled men, and 29.9% for non-disabled women according to a WHO Survey (applied in 51 countries); OECD, based on a 27 country analysis, estimates the employment rate of PWSN at 44%, compared with 75% of people without disabilities; the U.S. Bureau of Labour Statistics (2013) rates employment of PWSN at 18% compared to 64%. The Romanian figure is 12.7%, compared to 70% of the general population aged 18-55 (Alpha MDN, 2010).

The previous figures show undoubted inferior engagement of human resources with special needs on the labour force. Whereas there is some evidence that it could be a consequence of the nature of the work (Unger, 2002; Beegle and Stock, 2003; Jones and Sloane, 2010;) or dependency on social benefits (Acemoglu and Angrist, 2001), most evidence supports some facet of discrimination as the cause.

Discrimination is when a person cannot find work not because of its inability to work but as a repercussion of no accessibility (WHO, 2011). It is however illegal, in both private and public sectors, largely everywhere, as United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD), is universally adopted by all UN members, 193 countries. Moreover, there is vast and everchanging legislation, as well as policies, such as quotas, both at national and supranational levels.

Some of the most prominent theories aiming at understanding discrimination on the labour market are expectancy theory and statistical discrimination. Expectancy theory shows that when facing a hiring decision, employers, lacking information, will choose employees based on observable characteristics (Thurow, 1975; Reskin and Roos, 1990). Statistical discrimination explains choices regarding a person based on placing them in a category and then assessing their skills as the average of that group (Arrow, 1973; Lundberg and Startz, 1983). So, people have certain expectations and attitudes towards PWSN, not necessarily based on reality.

Attitudes differ dependent on the type of disability (Maroto and Pettinicchio, 2014), and once a firm hired an employee with a certain disability, it was more likely to hire other employees with the same disability (Unger, 2002).

Legislative methods can backfire and negatively impact attitudes (Maroto and Pettinicchio, 2014), some colleagues could develop negative attitudes towards PWSN because they associate them with less productivity and higher costs (Schwochau and Blanck, 2000; Unger, 2002). To conclude, this discrepancy suggests that previous experience can create more balanced and fair views about PWSN, reducing the uncertainty of hiring and promoting them in the workforce (Maroto and Pettinicchio, 2014).

Discussion and conclusions

In order to have a complete view, one has to analyse three characteristics: of the person with special needs, of the manager, and of the work. The first two construct various psychological attributes associated with managers, such as stereotypes, expectations, affective orientation. On the other hand, the characteristics of the work give expectations to the managers, which arise from the job interview and strictly from the results obtained from the done work. All these contour an image of the behaviour of the manager towards the person with special needs. The effect on the people inspires legislation and so forth, in a cyclical process. This can be visualized in Figure 1.

Despite benefits, legislation cannot lead to significant positive emotional changes for people with certain types of disabilities. The legislation may evoke negative reactions among employees if they are perceived as coercive or implemented as a preferential treatment for disabled applicants. Adherence to legislation can serve to perpetuate stereotypes and negative expectations, as observers may conclude that an individual with a disability has been hired because of legal requirements, rather than his or her ability to perform their job.

As determined by the research, people with disabilities should have greater access to organizations. Increased participation can serve to expand contact and interaction between people with disabilities and employers, and this communication can help change the expectations of others and overcome existing stereotypes about people with disabilities.

It is also aimed to create norms and values that can influence the experiences of people with disabilities in organizations. They identify the types of behaviours that are appropriate and provide moral justifications for organizational policies and practices.

These influence the formulation of organizational policies and practices. They clarify organizational objectives, direct organizational activities, and prescribe methods for achieving objectives. Thus, it is suggested that organizational policies and practices may affect people with disabilities because they influence job design, staffing methods, evaluation of procedures, and reward systems within organizations.

Figure 1. Model of Integration of Human Resources with Special Needs at the Organizational Level

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